

RESIDUAL THERMAL STRAINS IN A LAMINATED COMPOSITE

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INTRODUCTION

The thermal coefficients of expansion of a laminated composite are different in the fiber direction and in the direction perpendicular to the fibers. The contract of transverse direction of every lamina is much larger than that of longitudinal direction. When they are stacked together and sustain a temperature change, the deformation of every lamina will be restrained by its neighbors in different fiber directions. The composite is cured at elevated temperature while used at room temperature; therefore, residual strains and stresses will be produced on account of its anisotropic temperature deformation.

In general, it is supposed that a composite is thermal stress free at its curing temperature.

The thermal deformation of a composite cube has been investigated with moire interferometry. The strong edge effects, the interlaminar shear strains and the residual stresses resulted from the anisotropic thermal deformation are significant.

SPECIMEN

The specimen, as shown in fig.1, was cut from a thick-walled cylinder. Its stacking sequence was $[90/0]$, where the 0 deg fibers were parallel to the axis of the cylinder and 90 deg fibers were parallel to the hoop direction. It was cured at 250 F. The specimen grating was replicated on tow faces of the cube which were perpendicular to each other.

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

The in-plane displacements were obtained with moire interferometry and out-of-plane displacements were obtained with Twyman-Green interferometer. The wave length we used was 514.5 nm.

Tow faces which were perpendicular to each other were investigated separately.

In order to get the absolute in-plane displacements, tow techniques were developed. First, a ULE grating mold was used to replicate the specimen grating. ULE was ultra low expansion glass. Its thermal coefficient of expansion was low enough to be considered as zero.

The ULE grating mold was made at room temperature and its frequency was 1200 1/mm. Then the specimen grating was replicated at 250 F, which was supposed to be the thermal stress free temperature. The replicated material was a kind of epoxy glue which was cured at elevated temperature. The replication procedure was illustrated in fig.2. The ULE mold and specimen were heated first, and then the replication was done at 250 F. After the grating was cured completely, The specimen was separated from the mold and taken out of the oven and cooled down slowly. Since ULE's thermal expansion was negligible at elevated temperature, the frequency of the specimen grating was known exactly.

Secondly, the interferometry arrangement was adjusted with the original mold instead of specimen. The four-beam system, as shown in fig.3, was used to get the U-field and V-field displacements. The interferometry mirrors was illuminated by the coherent beam issued from the laser to form the virtual reference grating. The mirrors were adjusted to get the null field according to the mold. Then the frequency of the virtual grating was known as 2400 1/mm in this case.

The specimen was then put into the interferometer. The specimen mount could be adjusted around three coordinate axes. The second order diffraction beam coming from the specimen grating was adjusted to go back to the beam expander; then the U-field fringe pattern was adjusted to be symmetric.

Figure 4 shows the U, V and W field fringe patterns of Face A and Figure 5 shows the U, V and W field fringe pattern of Face B.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The fringe patterns show the strain and are essentially constant throughout the central region. the average strains of the cube are obtained according to the equations of moire interferometry which are shown in Fig.3.

$$\epsilon_x = -520 \cdot 10^{-6} ;$$

$$\epsilon_y = -6840 \cdot 10^{-6} ;$$

$$\epsilon_z = -1/5 \cdot 10^{-6}$$

Consequently, the thermal coefficients of the cube are:

$$\alpha_x = 3.00 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ 1/ F } ;$$

$$\alpha_y = 39.5 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ 1/ F } ;$$

$$\alpha_z = 1.01 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ 1/ F}$$

Large interlaminar shear strains are produced because of the different contraction of different layers. The variation of the shear strain along the interface is shown in Fig.6. The shear strains decrease sharply at the edges and tend to become zero about the zone of 4 or 6 ply thickness. The maximum peak value of them is 1.7%.

The vertical strains of 0 deg ply and 90 deg ply should have same values in the interior of the material. They are shown different at the surface because the contraction of laminae with different fiber orientation is different.

For Face A, the ratio of the vertical strain of 0 deg ply and 90 deg ply is 1.5; for Face B, the ratio of them is 0.57. It is considered as surface effect.

The different contraction of laminae with different fiber orientation is also the reason of the out-of-plane deformation of the specimen. For Face A, 0 deg ply contract more than 90 deg ply in the z direction; consequently, 90 deg plies protrude 0.8 mm to 1 mm above the 0 deg plies. For Face B, the difference is 1.4 mm to 1.6 mm.

As shown in Fig.7, there are shear stresses between different plies. In order to balance those shear stresses, there must be normal stresses in the ply. The integral of normal stress across the thickness of the ply should be equal to the integral of shear stress at the top and bottom surface of the ply. In other words, it should be equal to twice as the area under the shear stress curve. The normal stress always gives the matrix an extension and fibers a compression.

CONCLUSION

Moire interferometry is a powerful technique to investigate the deformation of composites. A specimen grating is applied to the composite at its stress-free temperature with ULE mold and its deformation is measured at room temperature with pre-adjusted interferometer. With this method, the absolute normal and shear strains can be obtained. Our results show that the strong edge effect, the interlaminar shear strain and residual stress due to the anisotropic thermal deformation should be brought to enough attention.

Fig.1. Specimen-a composite cube

Fig.2. Procedure of replication

$$\sin \alpha = f\lambda/2 ; f = 2400 \text{ lines/mm}$$

$$U = N_x/f ; V = N_y/f$$

$$\epsilon_x = \frac{\partial U}{\partial x} ; \epsilon_y = \frac{\partial V}{\partial y}$$

$$\gamma_{xy} = \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial V}{\partial x}$$

Fig.3 Moire interferometry system

RESIDUAL
THERMAL
STRAINS

FACE A

Fig. 4. Fringe pattern
of Face A

RESIDUAL
THERMAL
STRAINS

FACE B

Fig. 5. Fringe pattern
of Face B

SHEAR STRAIN AT THE EDGE

Fig. 6. Interlaminar shear strains

Fig. 7. Residual stress analysis